

Supplementary Material for "GPAS: Multi-Objective Genetic Programming with AUC and Separability Measures for Multiclass Classification"

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1 Introduction

This is the supplementary material for the paper entitled "GPAS: Multi-Objective Genetic Programming with AUC and Separability Measures for Multiclass Classification", including the following three sections: Section 2 compares GPAS with six traditional machine learning (ML) algorithms. Section 3 presents an experimental comparison of different transformation references, including the first quartile, the mean, the median, and the minimum output values of GP classifiers on the training set. Section 4 provides an analysis of the training time of GPAS and other GP-based methods.

2 Comparison of GPAS with six traditional ML methods

To evaluate the performance of our proposed GPAS method against other traditional ML algorithms, we compared GPAS with six algorithms: k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Decision Tree (DT), Naive Bayes (NB), Neural Network (NN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Random Forest (RF) [3]. All of these algorithms are implemented based on the scikit-learn library [2] using default parameters. Table. 1 shows the comparison results between GPAS and the six traditional ML algorithms.

As shown in Table. 1, GPAS only achieves the best performance only on the Cmc and Cle datasets. However, on the other datasets, GPAS consistently ranks among the top-performing methods, demonstrating its robustness. As illustrated in Fig. 1, GPAS attains the second-best overall rank, only slightly behind RF. It is worth noting that RF is an ensemble-based method, whereas GPAS is a non-ensemble approach. Despite this, GPAS achieves comparable performance. In addition, GP-based methods are capable of discovering relationships among features and possess implicit feature selection capabilities, which provide a certain degree of interpretability [1]. The literature [1] reports the relationship between

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Table 1. Comparison of GPAS with six traditional ML algorithms.

Dataset	Method	Mean	Std	Dataset	Method	Mean	Std
Tae	KNN	41.39	6.95	Cle	KNN	21.23	2.32
	DT	62.96	6.57		DT	29.80	3.14
	NB	52.50	6.88		NB	31.75	4.72
	NN	46.91	5.48		NN	29.43	3.67
	SVM	36.88	6.58		SVM	20.00	4.28
	RF	59.72	7.20		RF	30.49	4.01
	GPAS	56.50	4.40		GPAS	32.72	3.95
Movement	KNN	70.87	4.07	Ecoli	KNN	63.53	2.79
	DT	65.28	5.07		DT	52.75	7.46
	NB	62.33	3.34		NB	52.78	4.95
	NN	70.60	3.45		NN	35.48	4.95
	SVM	76.35	3.52		SVM	64.36	1.65
	RF	79.35	4.17		RF	61.05	5.40
	GPAS	72.60	4.26		GPAS	61.54	5.11
Vehicle	KNN	64.74	2.63	Cmc	KNN	48.34	1.89
	DT	69.81	2.69		DT	45.08	1.96
	NB	45.94	3.28		NB	49.53	2.16
	NN	64.12	4.30		NN	52.50	2.12
	SVM	49.39	2.50		SVM	44.46	1.60
	RF	75.05	2.10		RF	49.58	1.87
	GPAS	72.94	2.74		GPAS	54.12	1.87
Segment	KNN	93.56	0.73	Waveform	KNN	81.25	0.99
	DT	96.08	0.71		DT	73.99	1.01
	NB	79.69	1.08		NB	80.13	0.63
	NN	93.73	1.24		NN	83.49	0.90
	SVM	85.92	1.09		SVM	86.92	0.82
	RF	97.48	0.41		RF	85.25	0.83
	GPAS	88.31	1.59		GPAS	85.94	0.74

interpretability and performance for several machine learning algorithms, indicating a trade-off between the two. GP-based methods are considered highly interpretable, second only to DT. Notably, the proposed GPAS achieves performance close to RF while retaining relatively high interpretability, demonstrating a favorable balance between model performance and interpretability.

3 Comparison of GPAS with different transformation references

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the reference-based label prediction method in GPAS, we compared the results of using the median, mean, and minimum output values of the training samples from the GP classifier as reference points. The comparison results are shown in Table 2.

As shown in Table 2, GPAS achieves the best performance on the Tae, Cle, Movement, Ecoli, Cmc, and Segment datasets, while maintaining competitive re-

Fig. 1. Post-hoc test results for Table 1. Connected classifiers are not significantly different (at $p = 0.05$).

Table 2. Comparison of GPAS different transformation references.

Dataset	Method	Mean	Std	Dataset	Method	Mean	Std
Tae	Median	46.00	4.93	Cle	Median	31.38	2.73
	Mean	48.19	6.71		Mean	30.97	2.35
	Last	48.89	7.38		Last	31.00	4.28
	GPAS	56.50	4.40		GPAS	32.72	3.95
Movement	Median	67.48	8.03	Ecoli	Median	61.20	5.51
	Mean	66.88	8.51		Mean	61.21	5.40
	Last	65.07	6.67		Last	57.00	6.37
	GPAS	72.60	4.26		GPAS	61.54	5.11
Vehicle	Median	72.65	2.24	Cmc	Median	53.75	1.56
	Mean	72.72	2.68		Mean	54.14	1.17
	Last	73.92	1.99		Last	52.84	0.65
	GPAS	72.94	2.74		GPAS	54.12	1.87
Segment	Median	87.56	1.96	Waveform	Median	85.87	0.32
	Mean	87.62	1.93		Mean	85.85	0.35
	Last	76.57	4.63		Last	83.82	2.44
	GPAS	88.31	1.59		GPAS	85.94	0.74

Fig. 2. Post-hoc test results for Table 2. Connected classifiers are not significantly different (at $p = 0.05$).

sults on the Vehicle and Waveform datasets. Furthermore, as illustrated in Fig. 2,

Table 3. The training time of WMGP+, CC-MOGP, ASMiGP, and GPAS.

Dataset	WMGP+	CC-MOGP	ASMiGP	GPAS
Tae	21.63	335.15	950.01	132.31
Cle	53.63	3748.34	2968.58	206.88
Movement	165.63	35639.19	15717.01	615.55
Ecoli	63.05	3492.63	2169.23	276.89
Vehicle	91.25	2740.94	1718.35	195.70
Cmc	168.26	3312.28	2793.76	313.93
Segment	314.95	54372.66	7329.08	807.69
Waveform	251.62	27419.11	5369.74	1302.63

GPAS attains the best overall performance ranking. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of using the first quartile as the reference point.

4 Training Time Analysis

Table 3 presents the average training time (in seconds) of WMGP+, CC-MOGP, ASMiGP, and GPAS over 30 independent runs on eight benchmark datasets. Since M4GP was implemented using a different framework, it is not included in this comparison. It can be observed that the population-based iterative methods (WMGP+ and GPAS) require significantly less training time than the archive-based methods (CC-MOGP and ASMiGP). This is mainly because archive-based approaches must maintain an external archive and compare each newly generated individual against the archive members before updating the archive, introducing considerable additional computational overhead during evolution. As a result, their training times are substantially longer than those of population-based methods, especially on larger datasets.

As shown in Table 3, GPAS consistently requires less training time than CC-MOGP and ASMiGP across all datasets, while requiring only slightly more training time than WMGP+. The slightly shorter training time of WMGP+ may be attributed to its use of the number of leaf nodes as an additional optimization objective, which tends to constrain model complexity and reduce the search space. However, the ablation analysis in Section 5.2 shows that, for GPAS, incorporating an objective based on the number of leaf nodes leads to a deterioration in predictive performance. Therefore, GPAS does not include the number of leaf nodes as an optimization objective. Exploring more effective bloat control mechanisms that improve model compactness without sacrificing classification performance remains an important direction for future research.

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